

Optimal Design of a Compliant Tetra Joint via Computer-Aided Engineering Tools

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Abstract—In this study, our primary focus is to enhance the mobility of a compliant spherical joint known as the Tetra II joint. The Tetra II joint's range of motion is limited by its inner layers, which restrict its practicality in specific applications. To overcome this limitation, we employ a computer-aided engineering (CAE) framework and pseudo-rigid body (PRB) modeling to optimize the configuration of the Tetra II joint. Furthermore, we employed finite-element models (FEM) and simulations to validate the outcomes of the optimization process and to investigate the influence of various geometries. The resultant optimized joint, named Tetra III, is then compared with Tetra II, considering aspects such as range of motion and center shift. Our findings underscore the significant impact of triangle type selection on the joint's rotational capabilities, highlighting that the Tetra III design, based on an obtuse triangle, offers a notably improved range of motion. Finally, we fabricate the Tetra III joint, providing a tangible demonstration of its manufacturability.

Index Terms—Compliant Mechanisms, Tetra, Spherical Joint.

I. INTRODUCTION

Compared to rigid-body mechanisms, compliant mechanisms derive their motion and force transfer through the deformation of flexible components. This approach offers several benefits, including frictionless movement and the elimination of backlash. Furthermore, compliant joints demand fewer components for operation and can be designed to be more compact. The elimination of contact between rigid surfaces decreases wear, and the requirement for lubrication, all of which enhance the precision of the compliant mechanisms [1].

Spherical compliant joints present a precise alternative to conventional ball-and-socket joints. They utilize the bending of slender components to enable motion, effectively eliminating the friction and backlash typically found in traditional joints with rolling and sliding surfaces [2]. The literature presents several designs of spherical compliant joints capable of enabling three rotations at a single point. [3]–[6]. Most recently, Rommers et al. [2] developed Tetra joints by serially connecting tetrahedron-shaped elements without intermediate

Fig. 1: (a) Tetra II; (b) Deflected Tetra II; (c) Tetra III; (d) Deflected Tetra III

bodies. We deem the Tetra II joint particularly suited for compliant robots because of its compactness, and its "self-supporting" design which makes it easily producible with additive manufacturing.

In our prior research, we introduced a monolithic delta robot [7] that employs compliant spherical joints. These joints have been optimized based on the Tetra II joint (Fig. 1 (a) [2]), as presented in this paper. The Tetra II joint consists of interconnected tetrahedron-shaped elements arranged in a nested configuration. Each element includes blade flexures and connects directly without intermediary components. Within the Tetra II design, point P functions as the floating remote center of rotation, positioned in space (Fig. 1 (b)). The blade flexures effectively constrain the end-effector, enabling unrestricted rotations around point P. As shown in Fig. 1 (b),

Fig. 2: (a) Spatial PRB model; and (b) FE model of the three types of triangles.

when a horizontal force is applied at the end-effector, the joint undergoes rotation about point P, resulting in a spherical motion centered around point P.

This study aims to improve previous joint (Tetra II) by tackling the problem of joint stiffness caused by self-collisions, which restricts their usefulness in certain applications like monolithic delta robots. We suggest a design alteration to Rommers et al.'s model [2], illustrated in Fig. 1 (c), that reduces inner tetrahedral components to prevent self-collision-induced stiffness and enhance joint mobility.

Tetra III follows the same design and operational principles as Tetra II, as depicted in Figure 1 (d). Unlike Tetra II, Tetra III achieves optimal mobility without inner components, eliminating the stiffening observed in Tetra II. Consequently, Tetra III offers enhanced joint mobility by preventing self-collisions among inner components, thereby expanding the joint's overall range of motion compared to Tetra II.

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE OPTIMIZATION METHOD

In order to enhance Tetra joints' range of motion and streamline their fabrication, we investigated the importance of triangle types in their design. We employed a CAE framework for PRB modeling [8], to optimize the outer layer of the Tetra II joint. Specifically, we utilized a PRB modeling approach (fixed-guided flexible element) for each of the three beams within the Tetra II joint. Figure 2 (a) illustrates the PRB model for the Tetra II's outer layer.

To validate the results of the software-driven optimization, we constructed three tetrahedrons using acute, obtuse, and right triangles, as depicted in Figure 2 (b). It is worth noting that these triangles share identical perimeters, allowing us to compare them across three Euler rotations. Each tetrahedron underwent rotations in both positive and negative directions along the X, Y, and Z axes within RecurDyn. We recorded their maximum rotations, either at the point of maximum yield strength or upon collision with their edges.

Lastly, we designed the optimized Tetra joint, referred to as Tetra III, and conducted a comparative assessment with Tetra II regarding their range of motion and center shift.

III. EXEMPLARY RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

This study utilized a CAE framework and PRB modeling to optimize the Tetra II joint's configuration for maximizing its range of motion. The optimization results yielded an angle of 120 degrees and a length of 66.56 mm for the

Fig. 3: (a) Sum of the rotations (absolute values) for the three types of triangles; (b) The sum of the absolute values of rotations and center shifts of Tetra II and III.

Fig. 4: 3D-printed Tetra III

triangle. Validation has been conducted through FEM analysis, comparing various triangle designs. Results showed that the obtuse triangle design, as implemented in Tetra III (Fig. 3 (a)), outperformed acute and right triangles in all three Euler angles (yaw, pitch, and roll). This underscores the effectiveness of the optimization method and the triangle's pivotal role in influencing joint performance. The Tetra III design, featuring an obtuse isosceles triangle, offers an improved range of motion and even load distribution, enhancing joint stability and performance (see Fig. 3 (b)). The final stage involved SLS technology to fabricate the Tetra III joint, demonstrating its manufacturability (Fig. 4).

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